

Alliance Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum

Meeting Summary – 5th December 2023

Introduction

On 5th December 2023, the UK Health Data Research Alliance (the Alliance) convened the inaugural Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum meeting chaired by Professor Matthew Sydes (University College London) and Associate Professor Marion Mafham (University of Oxford). This was the first of a series of meetings, which will take place 3 times a year to facilitate an exchange of ideas between data providers, consumers of trial results and the wider trials community, covering how current challenges in the use of healthcare systems data (HSD) can be addressed and to prioritise the necessary actions to realise the potential benefits.

More than 50 participants from the health research and clinical trials ecosystem attended the meeting, including research groups, regulators, data custodians, funders, clinicians, and academic researchers. Please see the Appendix for a list of organisations represented at this meeting.

The session aimed to achieve the following objectives:

1. Articulate the forum rationale, purpose, and the challenges in delivering data-enabled trials.
2. Share examples of achievable solutions to overcome the challenges in delivering data-enabled trials.
3. Explain the importance of high-quality datasets.
4. Establish key priorities and next steps.

All presentations from the meeting can be found on the [UK Health Data Research Alliance website](#).

David Seymour and Rhoswyn Walker: Health Data Research UK and the UK Health Data Research Alliance

The meeting began with a presentation from Rhoswyn Walker (Director of Strategy, HDR UK) and David Seymour (Director of Infrastructure and Services, HDR UK) to provide an introduction to HDR UK and the UK Health Data Research Alliance, stressing the importance of bringing experts together to accelerate work on clinical trials based on healthcare systems data. The slides from this session can be found [here](#).

Matthew Sydes: Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum Introduction

Following on from the initial introduction, Matthew Sydes provided further context regarding the forum rationale and the challenges faced by researchers and clinicians when using healthcare systems data to enable clinical trials. Following on from Matthew's presentation, Marion Mafham highlighted key points from the forum terms of reference and explained the nuanced role this forum would play. The Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation forum will be convened as part of the Transforming Data for Trials forum, a HDR UK core funded programme.

The slides from this session can be found [here](#). Terms of reference can be found [here](#). Comments on the draft are welcome.

Mike Robling: Priority setting the opportunities for routinely collected data and trials: COMORANT--UK

Professor Mike Robling (Director of Population Health and Social Care Trials, Cardiff University's Centre for Trials Research) presented slides detailing the COMORANT-UK study and the actual and perceived challenges of using routinely collected healthcare systems data to enable trials research. Mike's slides detailed the study's methodology, stakeholders, delivery, and results. The delivery of this study helped formulate consensus and agreement around [7 top priority challenges to address](#). These were brought to a virtual consensus meeting in which stakeholders agreed a list of priorities.

The slides from this session can be found [here](#).

Tim Williams: CPRD data quality work: Assuring quality of datasets – Lessons from CPRD

Dr Tim Williams (Head of Interventional Research, Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD)) presented slides highlighting the impact of CPRD data on public health, their interventional research services and CPRD's data quality strategy, including principles and objectives. CPRD have now implemented a data quality strategy and will be developing a series of data quality projects, including identifying the minimum standards for using ethnicity and primary care records.

The slides from this session can be found [here](#).

Marion Mafham and Charlie Harper: HDR UK Transforming Data for Trials: data utility comparisons

Marion Mafham (Associate Professor, Oxford Population Health, University of Oxford) and Charlie Harper (Medical Statistician, Oxford Population Health, University of Oxford) presented slides on data utility comparison studies (DUCKS) and the need to understand biases while communicating the credibility of new methodologies to regulators and relevant stakeholders. Charlie gave an insight into A Study of Cardiovascular Events in Diabetes (ASCEND), a randomised trial of 15,480 UK people with diabetes and no prior vascular disease between 2005 and 2007.

The slides from this session can be found [here](#).

Key discussion points:

The group discussed the following questions:

- Do we agree that data utility comparison studies (DUCKS) are important and should be supported?
- How do we enable this kind of methods research?
- Who do we need to engage to enable these studies to be done?

Given the longer collection period and changes in HSD, there was speculation that differences may be greater than clinical trial data. This question was raised in response to Charlie's presentation. Marion explained that data in these studies are 'matured' with a large time gap following the scheduled treatment period (allowing for updates). The censored time point for the analysis is the same in both datasets, except time has been allowed for missing data to be collected. There were suggestions that analysis could be conducted at various time points to examine consistency of HSD.

It is very difficult to find funding for this kind of methodological work and to publish it as the direct path to impact is difficult to articulate. It was suggested that this could be tied in with funding for current research, where possible. The real value comes from repeating these studies as many researchers would be reluctant to base their study design on one case study.

Thinking about DUCKS in a collaborative framework would help make the results more discoverable. Replication of this study with other trial datasets is already in progress. As a group, it is important to encourage more of these types of studies and to make them more visible.

There were queries on how much these studies cost, and if unknown, how do we ensure this is known for future studies.

Marion confirmed that there are two notable costs: funding skilled staff who conduct the work and access to linked data. Researchers are well versed in the former, but the latter is often not sufficiently considered (nor easily costed) during in funding applications. It was further acknowledged that accessing data is a lengthy process, and this can make these studies expensive in terms of staff resourcing.

Moving on from funding queries, it was suggested that if DUCKS are part of an evidence base-to encourage trial sponsors to use HSD more, then national-level support would assist data providers in making data more accessible for these purposes. This may be a good strategic goal for this group.

Finally, there was a discussion about the measures of agreement used, and which dataset is considered the reference (i.e. gold standard). A kappa statistic for interrater reliability is preferred over sensitivity and specificity. For some trials, adjudicated outcomes would be the reference dataset, but where there is no adjudication, the analysis may be more of a comparison between two data sources rather than one being a reference.

Next steps:

Following this introductory meeting, participants were encouraged to continue contributing to the Jamboard (for discussion) that was shared after the final presentation. This could be accessed [here](#) and will remain open. Your feedback here will inform the key priorities of this forum and the challenges that we wish to address.

Future meetings have been scheduled as below.

- Thursday 18th April 2024 (14:00 – 15:30)
- Wednesday 11th September 2024 (14:00 – 15:00)

An agenda and Eventbrite registration link for the next meeting will be shared with all participants shortly. If you have suggestions for discussion topics, please share your ideas with us.

Appendix

Contributing Organisations
AbbVie
Association of Medical Research Charities.
Bristol Trials Centre
Cancer Research UK
Centre for Trials Research, Cardiff University
Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD)
Cystic Fibrosis Trust
Cystic Fibrosis Trust
EMIS
Health & Social Care Delivery Research programme
Health Data Research UK
Imperial College Health Partners
Imperial College London
Imperial's Clinical Trials and the Neonatal Analysis Units
Intensive Care National Audit & Research Centre (ICNARC)
MRC Clinical Trials Unit
National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
NHS Data for Research and Development Programme (NHSE)
NHS DigiTrials (NHSE)
NIHR Clinical Research Network
NIHR HTA Research Funding programme
Nuffield Department of Primary Care Health Sciences
Observational & Pragmatic Research Institute (OBRI)
Office of Clinical Trials for Health Canada
Optimum Patient Care
Pfizer
Queen's University Belfast
The Brain Tumour Charity
UK Clinical Research Collaboration Clinical Trials Unit Network

UK Dementia Research Institute

UK Dementia Research Institute

UK Kidney Association

UK Kidney Association

UK National Neonatal Research Database
--

Understanding Patient Data

University College London

University of Aberdeen

University of Oxford
